

A Study on the Attitude of Women towards Organically Grown Foods with Respect to Health, Environment and Pricing

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:
Prabhakar, Avanti.
“A Study on the Attitude of Women towards Organically Grown Foods with Respect to Health, Environment and Pricing.” *Shanlax Internatioal Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 23–29.

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586370>

Dr. (Mrs.) Avanti Prabhakar

Assistant Professor

Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Home Science

Justice Basheer Ahmed Sayeed College for Women (Autonomous), Chennai

Abstract

The aim of the present investigation is to study the Attitude of Women towards Organically Grown Foods with respect to Health, Environment and Pricing. The main study was conducted on a randomly selected sample of 120 subjects. The subjects were divided into equal numbers; 60 working women and 60 home makers. They were again sub-divided based on their monthly family income, as 30 women with income greater than Rs. 50,000 and 30 women with income less than Rs. 50,000 per month. The sample was further divided according to their educational qualification as well, as 15 postgraduates and 15 undergraduates. The same was repeated for the other category respectively. The attitude of women towards organic foods for the present study was assessed using a modified questionnaire by Stacey Paterson (2015). The data collected was tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using arithmetic mean, standard deviation, student's t-test and Karl person's coefficient of correlation test. The results of this investigation indicated that there was no significant difference in attitude of women towards health, environment and pricing based on their educational qualification and monthly family income. There was a significant difference in knowledge on organic foods based on the monthly family income. The women who were having the family income less than Rs.50000/- a month and women who had higher family income and were post graduates exhibited better knowledge on organic foods. A positive relationship was found between the attitude and knowledge on organic foods based on educational qualification and monthly family income. Hence, it was concluded that, higher educational qualification and family income, are the most influential factors determining the attitude and knowledge of women towards organic foods.

Keywords: Attitude, Organic foods, Health, Environment, Pricing.

Introduction

Food is the edible or potable substance (usually of animal or plant origin), consisting of nourishing and nutritive components such as carbohydrates, fats, proteins, essential mineral and vitamins, which sustains life, generates energy and provides growth, maintenance and health of the body. (businessdictionary.com)

Organic Foods

An 'Organic food' is the product of a farming system which avoids the use of man-made fertilizers, pesticides, growth regulators and livestock feed additives. Irradiation and the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) or products produced from or by GMOs are generally prohibited by organic legislation (Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs U K).

For the vast majority of its history, agriculture can be described as having been organic; only during the 20th century was a large supply of new products, generally deemed not organic, introduced into food production. The organic farming movement arose in the 1940s in response to the industrialization of agriculture. There are more than 100 countries growing organic foods and producing organic products. Ninety of these countries are developing countries with perfect climatic conditions to produce the best organic product (Krystallis & Chrystohoidis, 2005).

Perceived Benefits of organic Food

- Organic produce contains fewer pesticides.
- Organic foods are often fresher.
- Organic farming is better for the environment.
- Organically raised animals are not given antibiotics, growth hormones or fed animal byproducts.
- Organic meat and milk are richer in certain nutrients.
- Organic food is GMO (Genetically modified organisms) free.

Disadvantages of organic Foods

- Higher price
- Time and skill
- Faster Spoilage
- Higher risk of infection
- Specific Location availability

There is widespread public belief that organic food is safer, more nutritious and better tasting than conventional food, which has largely contributed to the development of an organic food culture. Consumers purchase organic foods for different reasons, including concerns about the effects of conventional farming practices on the environment, human health and animal welfare. Hence organic food promoters suggest that greater consumption of organic foods reduces chronic illness, cancer and even helping in combating obesity. Because of this there is increase in demands and high scope for organic foods.

According to a report by Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, India ranks 11th among 170 exporters of organic produce and ninth in terms of area under organic cultivation. While India follows regulatory standards set by the Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA), when it comes to export of organic products, there is currently no regulation governing its domestic market and imports.

Literature review

A variety of factors that can potentially influence organic food consumption have been studied in relevant literature-

Organic foods are more preferred by women over conventional foods due to factors like health, food safety, taste, freshness, environmental concern, and animal welfare (Hughner et al., 2007; Magnusson, Arvola, Hursti, Åberg, & Sjöden, 2001; Schifferstein & Ophuis, 1998; Torjusén, Lieblein, Wandel, & Francis, 2001; Wandel & Bugge, 1997; Zanolli & Naspetti, 2002). Research

reveals that women consumers are show better willingness towards purchase of organic foods (Briggeman& Lusk, 2011;Tsakiridou, Boutsouki, Zotos, & Mattas, 2008;van), which indicate the better adaptability to natural foods by women consumers (Krystallis&Chryssohoidis, 2005). Studies concluded that women are more willing to pay a premium price for environmentally friendly foods (Loureiro, McCluskey, &Mittelhammer, 2001, 2002)

Demographic and socioeconomic variables, like age, marital status, income, education and family size, are instrumental factors in determining demand, awareness and buying behavior towards organic foods (Wier et al., 2003). The majority of international articles revealed that educated consumers have ainclined attitude and purchase intentions towards organic foods. (Magnusson et al., 2001; Fotopoulos and Krystallis, 2002; Tsakiridou et al., 2008)

Many studies were conducted comparing the taste and nutritional value of organically grown foods versus conventionally grown food. Most studies concluded that there is not much difference between the taste and nutritional content of organic and conventional foods (Woese, Lange, Boess and Bogl Werner 1999). In addition, dependent on the quality and price of the products, certain age groups and women are more likely to purchase organic foods because of their beliefs that organic food is better for their health. (Lea &Worsley, 2005)Women are the major purchaser of the farm produces also they are the primary caregivers with respect to the family health.

Therefore the purpose of the present investigation was to study the attitude of Indian women towards organically grown foodswith respect to health, environment and pricing. Thisinvestigation is highly significant, as there are no studies done on this aspect in Indian subcontinent. The study was taken up with the following broad objectives.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the attitude of women towards organically grown foods with respect to health, environment and pricing with regards to their working status.
- To assess the attitude of women towards organically grown foods with respect to health, environment and pricing based on their educational qualification.
- To assess the attitude of women towards organically grown foods with respect to health, environment and pricing based on the family income.

Methodology

Selection of area

For the purpose of present study, working women as subjects were selected from the teaching and non-teaching staff of JBAS College for Women and for the home-makers as subjects were chosen from nearby residential areas of the researcher.

Selection of sample

The sample for the present study was selected by Random sampling method. The total sample consists of 120 women based on the occupational status, educational qualification and monthly family income.

Distribution of Sample

The subjects were divided into equal numbers; 60 working women and 60 home makers. They were again sub-divided based on their monthly family income, as 30 women with income greater than Rs. 50,000 and 30 women with income less than Rs. 50,000 per month. The sample was further divided according to their educational qualification as well, as 15 postgraduates and 15 undergraduates. The same was repeated for the other category respectively.

Selection of Tool

The attitude of women towards organic food was assessed using modified questionnaire of Stacey Paterson (2015) for the present study.

Statistical Analyses

The data collected was tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using arithmetic mean, standard deviation, student's t-test and Karl person's coefficient of correlation test.

Results and Discussion

Only a few selected results of the investigation are presented herewith-

Table 1 shows the difference in knowledge about organically grown foods among undergraduate women having monthly family income below Rs. 50,000 and above Rs. 50,000.

Table 1 Knowledge about organically grown foods among undergraduate women having monthly family income below Rs. 50,000 and above Rs. 50,000

Variable	Monthly Family Income (Rs)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' value	Level of Significance
Knowledge	Below 50,000	30	27.13	2.751	2.342	p<0.05
	Above 50,000	30	25.40	2.979		

Note: p<0.05 significant at 5% level

The results in Table 1 revealed that there is a significant difference in knowledge about organically grown foods among undergraduate women having monthly family income below Rs. 50,000 and above Rs. 50,000 as the calculated 't' value (t=2.342) was higher than the table value t=1.96 at 5% level of significance, hence it is significant at 5% level.

Table 2 shows the difference in knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate and postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000.

Table 2 Knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate and postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000

Variable	Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' value	Level of Significance
Knowledge	Undergraduate	30	27.13	2.751	2.064	p>0.01
	Postgraduate	30	25.27	4.118		

Note: p>0.05 significant at 1% level

The results in Table 2 showed that there is a significant difference in knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate and postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000 as the calculated 't' value (t=2.064) is high than the table value t=1.96 at 1% level of significance, hence it is significant.

The results supported the study done by Janiak, Orzechowska-Przybyla and Lesiow (2016) who aimed to assess knowledge and behaviour among consumers on the organic food market. The results indicated that major part of the consumers had sufficient knowledge for consciously purchasing and consuming organic foods.

Table 3 shows the relationship between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs.50, 000.

Table 3 Attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000

Variable	Knowledge	Level of Significance
Attitude	0.649**	p>0.01

The results in Table 3 revealed that there exists a positive correlation at 1% level between the attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000 as the value of correlation was found to be 0.649.

The results supports the findings of Antonio et al.,(2014) who assessed the knowledge about chemical components in Organic foods among consumers. The results revealed that the knowledge has an impact on the purchasing power among consumers.

Table 4 shows the relationship between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income above Rs. 50,000.

Table 4 Attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income above Rs. 50,000

Variable	Knowledge	Level of Significance
Attitude	0.534**	p>0.01

The results in Table 4 indicated that there exists a positive correlation at 1% level between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among undergraduate women belonging to monthly family income above Rs. 50,000, as the value of correlation was found to be 0.649.

Table 5 shows the relationship between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000.

Table 5 Attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000

Variable	Knowledge	Level of Significance
Attitude	0.406*	p<0.05

The results in Table 5 signifies that there exists a positive correlation at 5% level between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among postgraduate women belonging to monthly family income below Rs. 50,000, as the value of correlation was found to be 0.649.

Table 6 shows the relationship between attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among postgraduate women belonging to above monthly family income Rs. 50,000.

Table 6 Attitude and knowledge towards organically grown foods among postgraduate women belonging to above monthly family income Rs. 50,000

Variable	Knowledge	Level of Significance
Attitude	0.723**	p>0.01

The results in Table 6 reveals that there exists a positive correlation at 1% level between and knowledge towards organically grown foods among post-graduate women belonging to above monthly family income Rs. 50,000, as the value of correlation was found to be 0.649.

The finding supports the result of Zanoli and Naspetti (2002) who presented the consumer perception and knowledge of organic foods and related behavior. The results showed that difference exists between groups of consumers with respect to their experience and knowledge of Organic foods.

Conclusion

The results of this investigation indicated that there was no significant difference in attitude of women towards health, environment and pricing based on their educational qualification and monthly family income. There was a significant difference in knowledge on organic foods based on the monthly family income. The women who were having the family income less than Rs.50000/- a month and women who had higher family income and were post graduates exhibited better knowledge on organic foods. This could be attributed to higher pricing of organic foods and higher education among two groups respectively. A positive relationship was found between the attitude and knowledge on organic foods based on educational qualification and monthly family income. Hence, it was concluded that, higher educational qualification and family income, are the most influential factors determining the attitude and knowledge of women towards organic foods. More extensive research is crucial in this area owing to increased demands and scope for organic foods.

Scope for Further Research

1. To compare the attitude towards Organically Grown Foods with respect to Health, Environment and Pricing between men and women.
2. To analyze the attitude towards Organically Grown Foods with respect to Health, Environment and Pricing among women of different age groups.
3. To undertake a pre and posttest investigation after providing an intervention program pertaining to awareness on Organically Grown Foods to women.

References

1. Antonio, G. M. A., Fernanda, H. M. M., Araceli, R. G., Regina, E. V., Augusto, M. G. A., & Carlos, R. L. J. (2014). Consumer knowledge about the chemical composition of organic foods.
2. Brian C. Briggeman, Jayson L. Lusk. (2011). Preferences for fairness and equity in the food system, *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, Volume 38, Issue 1, pp 1–29,
3. Fotopoulos, C., & Krystallis, A. (2002) Organic product avoidance: Reasons for rejection and potential buyers' identification in a countrywide survey, *British Food Journal*, Vol. 104 Issue: 3/4/5, pp.233-260,
4. Hughner, R.-S., et al. (2007). Who Are Organic Food Consumers? A Compilation and Review of Why People Purchase Organic Food. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 6, 94-110.
5. Janiak, E., Orzechowska-Przybyła, K., & Lesiów, T. (2016). Analysis of knowledge and consumer preferences in the field of organic food. *Nauki Inżynierskie i Technologie*, (1 (20).
6. Krystallis, A., & Chrysosoidis, G. (2005). Consumers' willingness to pay for organic food: Factors that affect it and variation per organic product type. *British Food Journal*, 107(5), 320-343.
7. Loureiro, Maria & McCluskey, Jill. (2003). Consumer Preferences and Willingness to Pay for Food Labeling: A Discussion of Empirical Studies. *Journal of Food Distribution Research*. 34
8. Magnusson, K., Maria & Arvola, Anne & Hursti, Ulla-Kaisa & Åberg, Lars & Sjöden, Per-Olow. (2001). Attitudes towards organic foods among Swedish consumers. *British Food Journal*. 103. 209-227. 10.1108/00070700110386755.
9. Magnusson, M. K., Arvola, A., Koivisto Hursti, U.-K., Åberg, L., & Sjöden, P.-O. (2001). Attitudes towards organic foods among Swedish consumers. *British Food Journal*, 103, 209–226.

10. Paterson, S.(2015). Student Perceptions of Organic Food In Relation To Health, Environment And Pricing; Theses and Dissertations-Dietetics and Human Nutrition. 38. https://uknowledge.uky.edu/foodsci_etds/38
11. Schifferstein H.N.J., Oude Ophuis P.A.M. (1998). Health-related determinants of organic food consumption in the Netherlands, *Food Quality and Preference*, 3, 119-133,
12. Torjusen, H., Lieblein, G., Wandel, M., & Francis, C. A. (2001). Food System Orientation and Quality Perception among Consumers and Producers of Organic Food in Hedmark County, Norway. *Food Quality and Preference*, 12, 207-216.
13. Tsakiridou,E.,Boutsouki,C., Zotos,Y., &Mattas,K. (2008). Attitudes and behaviour towards organic products: an exploratory study, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 36 Issue: 2, pp.158-175,
14. Wandel, M., &Bugge, A. (1997). Environmental Concern in Consumer Evaluation of Food Quality. *Food Quality and Preference*, 8, 19-26.
15. Wier, Mette & Andersen, Laura &Millock, Katrin&O’Doherty Jensen, Katherine &Rosenkvist, Lars. (2005). Perceptions, values and behaviour: The case of organic foods. *Agriculture and Human Values*. 1.
16. Woese, K., Lange, D., Boess, C.& Werner Bögl, K.,(1999). A Comparison of Organically and Conventionally Grown Foods—Results of a Review of the Relevant Literature;*Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*V.74, Issue 3; P. 281-293
17. Zanolì, R., &Naspetti, S. (2002). Consumer motivations in the purchase of organic food: a means-end approach. *British food journal*, 104(8), 643-653.

Web References

1. <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/food.html>
2. <http://www.hempcanadabulk.com/organic-vs-conventional/>
3. <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-environment-food-rural-affairs>